

This article is made available by the Document Delivery Service of IRRI Library for personal scholarly, research, and educational use. Further distribution requires the permission of the copyright owner.

Seed size affected significantly seed yields for different grades in both varieties (Table 2). The graded seeds gave significantly higher yields than did the other seed grades. Ungraded and undersized seeds did not differ statistically in grain yield. Sujata, however, was significantly superior to Mahsuri for seed yield. The interaction between seed size and variety was not significant, which emphasizes the importance of grading for obtaining quality rice seed and for realizing a variety's yield potential. Using ungraded or undersized seed to produce a crop may adversely affect yield potential and should be discouraged.

No marked difference existed in the seed quality obtained from different grades of seeds. The main effect of seed size is on the production potential or grain yield and not on the quality of the seeds produced from them. ■

Competitive ability of medium-duration rices for grain yield

N. Kulkarni, Agricultural Research Institute (ARI), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Varietal mixtures differ in their efficiency in capturing resources to produce higher yields compared with when varieties are grown in pure stands. We studied the competitive ability of all possible mixtures of five varieties in 1992 and six varieties in 1993. These varieties had long, slender grains and medium duration (130-150 d). Two varieties were mixed in equal proportions, using all possible combinations.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design repeated three times during 1992 and 1993 wet seasons. Each entry was planted in a six-row plot, 5.4 m in length, and spaced at 15 cm between and within rows. One-month-old seedlings of the mixtures and of the pure varieties were planted in 1992 and 45-d-old seedlings in 1993.

Grain yield data and percent increase over best pure varieties and check Surekha were recorded (Table 1). In 1992, two varietal mixtures—RDR536 + Surekha and RDR536 + Saleem—yielded

Table 1. Grain yield of varietal mixtures and pure varieties.

Varietal mixture/ pure variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	% increase over	
		Best pure variety	Check variety
1992			
RDR536 + Raja Vadlu	8.2	0.0	21.1
RDR536 + Divya	8.0	-2.4	18.2
RDR536 + Surekha	9.4	14.6	39.9
RDR536 + Saleem	9.2	12.2	36.2
Raja Vadlu + Divya	6.8	-9.3	0.3
Raja Vadlu + Surekha	8.0	6.6	19.0
Raja Vadlu + Saleem	7.7	2.7	14.6
Divya + Surekha	7.6	11.7	12.0
Divya + Saleem	7.3	19.3	9.2
Surekha + Saleem	7.2	5.9	5.9
RDR536	8.2		
Raja Vadlu	7.5		
Divya	5.9		
Surekha	6.8		
Saleem	6.1		
CD	0.8		
CV (%)	5.6		
1993			
RDR536 + Raja Vadlu	5.8	9.3	12.6
RDR536 + Surekha	5.9	9.3	14.1
RDR536 + Saleem	4.9	-9.2	-4.9
RDR536 + RNR 32341	5.7	7.4	11.2
RDR536 + CSR13	6.0	11.1	12.7
Raja Vadlu + Surekha	5.9	15.7	14.1
Raja Vadlu + Saleem	4.8	0.0	1.9
Raja Vadlu + RNR32341	5.6	3.7	7.8
Raja Vadlu + CSR13	5.5	1.9	7.0
Surekha + Saleem	4.8	-5.9	-7.8
Surekha + RNR32341	5.4	0.0	5.6
Surekha + CSR13	5.2	-3.7	1.4
Saleem + RNR32341	5.4	0.0	5.6
Saleem + CSR13	4.5	-1.8	-11.9
RNR32341 + CSR13	5.3	-1.8	2.1
RDR536	5.4		
Raja Vadlu	4.8		
Surekha	5.1		
Saleem	4.6		
RNR32341	5.4		
CSR13	5.4		
CD	0.5		
CV (%)	4.8		

Table 2. General combining ability effects.^a

	1992	1993
RDR536	0.280**	0.153**
Raja Vadlu	0.004	-0.006
Divya	-0.191**	-
Surekha	-0.001	0.013
Saleem	-0.093*	-0.274**
CSR13	-	0.031
RNR32341	-	0.081
SE (g/t)	0.038	0.04

*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.

12% more grain than when planted individually and 36% more grain than Surekha. Other varietal mixtures also outyielded the check.

In 1993, Raja Vadlu + Surekha yielded 15.7% more than the best yields

of the sole varieties; RDR536 + Raja Vadlu, 9.3%; RDR536 + CSR13, 11.1%; and collectively, about 13% more than the check. These combinations were phenotypically uniform, which is desirable. The general combining ability effects are estimated in Table 2, treating the experiment as mechanical diallel. RDR536 in the various mixtures produced more grain and possessed significantly positive general combining ability effects in both years.

This study revealed superior performance of varietal mixtures compared with that of pure varieties. Therefore, it is worthwhile to test more varietal mixtures to exploit their competitive ability. ■

Pest resistance— insects

Resistance of medium-duration rice cultivars to caseworm and leafhopper

H. P. Patnaik, K. M. Samal, and S. Mohapatra, Regional Research Station, Keonjhar 758002, Orissa, India

Caseworm (CW) *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guenée) and leafhopper (LF) *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* (Guenée) incidences have been high in recent years in the rice-growing area of the north central plateau of Orissa State, India. We evaluated 12 promising medium-duration (120-135 d) rice cultivars for resistance to these pests during 1992 and 1993 wet seasons (WS).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Each cultivar was transplanted in 4 × 2-m plots. The percentage of leaves damaged by CW was recorded at 30 d after transplanting (DT) and that by LF at 50 DT. For each plot, we randomly selected 20 hills and examined five leaves per hill. Low precipitation (996 mm) in 1992 WS favored LF incidence while high precipitation (1200 mm) in 1993 WS favored CW incidence.

Cultivar RP2327-318 had high insect damage and low yields in both 1992 and 1993. In contrast, cultivar P622-629

Reaction of promising medium-duration rice cultivars to CW and LF infestation^a at Joshipur, Orissa, India. 1992 and 1993 WS.

Cultivar	Parentage	Duration (d)	Leaf damage (%)						Yield (t/ha)		
			CW			LF			1992	1993	Pooled mean
			1992	1993	Pooled mean	1992	1993	Pooled mean			
OR709-11 (IET11001)	IR36/Suph/IR3880//CR222/Parijat	120	1.6 (5.8) ^a	20.0 (26.1) c-e	10.8 (15.9)	20.7 (24.2)	2.0 (6.4)	11.3 (15.3)	2.4 def	4.0 bcd	3.2
P622-629 (IET11009)	Pusa 456/P502	130	4.8 (9.7)	28.0 (31.8) bcd	16.4 (20.7)	23.1 (21.2)	4.0 (8.8)	13.5 (15.0)	4.6 ab	4.6 ab	4.6
P586-6-10 (IET11006)	P150/IR20	120	1.3 (5.3)	26.0 (30.6) bcde	13.6 (17.9)	19.1 (25.8)	6.0 (13.9)	12.5 (19.8)	2.6 de	3.9 cde	3.2
OR698-22 (IET11000)	OR165-24-12/Sarathi	120	3.4 (8.2)	24.0 (29.3) bcde	13.7 (18.7)	9.9 (16.9)	8.0 (15.9)	8.9 (16.4)	2.6 de	3.8 def	3.2
RP233-310 (IET11494)	Ratna/ARC10659	120	2.5 (7.1)	28.0 (31.8) bcd	15.2 (19.4)	10.5 (18.3)	10.0 (18.3)	10.2 (18.3)	2.6 de	3.9 cdef	3.2
RP2327-318 (IET11765)	Ratna/ARC5981	125	0.0 (1.3)	52.0 (46.1) a	26.0 (23.7)	16.5 (23.9)	10.0 (17.5)	13.2 (20.7)	1.6 ef	3.7 defg	2.6
CR712-3-38	TN1/Mahiabankoi	135	10.1 (16.1)	32.0 (34.4) bc	21.0 (25.2)	11.7 (19.5)	2.0 (6.4)	6.8 (12.9)	5.0 a	4.7 a	4.8
OR378-1	IR2070-414/Mahsuri	120	0.0 (1.3)	18.0 (25.1) de	9.0 (13.2)	18.3 (23.0)	0.0 (1.3)	7.6 (12.1)	3.8 c	4.7 a	4.2
Lalat	Obs. 677/IR2071//Rp6-13/W1268	125	0.0 (1.3)	34.0 (35.4) b	17.0 (18.3)	11.1 (18.6)	6.0 (10.8)	8.5 (14.7)	4.6 ab	4.0 bcd	4.3
Sarasa	CR94-1512/Ratna	125	3.5 (8.3)	24.0 (29.3) bcde	13.7 (18.8)	12.3 (20.5)	6.0 (12.4)	10.1 (16.4)	2.6 de	4.5 abc	3.5
Sarathi	T90/IR8//W1263	120	2.1 (6.6)	34.0 (35.7) b	18.0 (21.1)	8.2 (16.2)	8.0 (13.9)	7.1 (15.0)	3.4 cd	3.4 defg	3.4
Srabani	Mahsuri/IR30	130	3.6 (10.8)	26.0 (30.6) bcde	14.8 (20.7)	8.5 (10.5)	4.0 (8.8)	6.2 (9.6)	5.0 a	3.8 de	4.4
CD ^b (P = 0.05)	-	-	ns ^c	9.1	ns	ns	ns	ns	1.0	0.6	ns

^aFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bCD = critical difference. ^cns = not significant by F-test.

(IET11009) yielded well despite high LF damage in 1992, and cultivars CR712-3-38 and P622-629 had high yields in 1993 despite high levels of CW damage (see table). This suggests that these cultivars may be resistant to damage by defoliating insects. ■

We evaluated 33 rice genotypes to study their reactions to these nematodes. Screening was done at IAAS in lightly flooded soils with natural infestations of *H. oryzae* and *H. mucronata*. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design and 5- × 3-m plots with three replicates during the 1992 rice-growing season. Recommended cultural practices were followed.

The nematode population was assessed at the maximum tillering stage of the rice crop. Four corner hills and one central hill were collected with about 250 cm³ of soil and mixed to prepare one core sample. From these, 3 g of roots and 200 cm³ of soil were separated, processed using a blender with modified Baermann trays, and sieved with modified Baermann trays. The results were analyzed using ANOVA and DMRT.

None of the varieties were resistant. All had nematode populations inside and outside of the roots (see table). Local variety Ghaiya 2, however, had significantly more nematodes in its roots than the other varieties and was considered to be the most susceptible. ■

Population densities^a (no.) of *Hirschmanniella* in different varieties at IAAS, Rampur, Nepal. 1992.

Variety	Root ^b	Soil ^c
NR604-1-1-2-4-1	3.3 a	4.3 a
IR79-21	3.6 a	4.0 a
RP1125-604-1-1	3.6 a	2.0 a
BR808-17-24	3.6 a	4.3 a
NR604-1-1-2-4-2	3.6 a	4.0 a
NR806-2-1-1-1	4.0 a	2.3 a
BR203-70-13-2	4.0 a	3.6 a
NR601-1-1-3-1-1-2	4.0 a	2.6 a
NR806-1-9-3	4.6 a	3.3 a
Radha 7	4.6 a	4.3 a
Acheme Masino	5.0 a	3.6 a
B4354-C-PN4	5.3 a	3.0 a
NR601-18-1-2-13-1	5.3 a	3.6 a
NR10136-9-6-21	5.3 a	3.6 a
NR605-9-1-1	6.0 a	2.3 a
Bindeshori	6.0 a	4.6 a
IR5167-3-50-2-1	6.3 a	1.6 a
NR650-2-3-2-1	6.6 a	4.6 a
Radha	6.6 a	4.6 a
IR15672-1-86-1-1	7.3 a	4.6 a
Janaki	9.0 a	9.6 a
Masuli	10.0 a	5.3 a
Makawanpur	13.0 a	10.0 a
Chaite 4	13.0 a	14.0 a
S499-13-28	13.0 a	4.6 a
Pant 4	15.0 a	2.6 a
Sarju 52	16.0 a	8.0 a
SIPI 692033	18.0 a	5.3 a
Radha 9	19.0 a	6.3 a
Chaite 2	22.0 a	3.6 a
Sabitri	27.0 a	10.0 a
Sarju 49	29.0 a	6.0 a
Ghaiya 2	150.0 b	10.0 a

^aIn a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bNumber per 3 g of root, av of 3 replicates. ^cNumber per 200 cm³ of soil, av of 3 replicates.)

Pest resistance— other pests

Rice genotype reaction to rice root nematode (*Hirschmanniella*) in Rampur, Nepal

R. R. Pokharel, Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science (IAAS), Central Campus, Rampur, Nepal

High densities of mixed populations of *Hirschmanniella oryzae* and *H. mucronata* are commonly found in heavy and frequently irrigated soils in lowland rice areas in the Terai region of Nepal.